

**EMPIRICAL STUDY EXPLORING THE LINK BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL
ONBOARDING PROGRAMS AND EMPLOYEE RETENTION AMONG
EMPLOYEES OF SELECTED PRIVATE BUSINESS
ORGANIZATIONS IN QUEZON CITY**

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Empirical Study Exploring the Link Between Organizational Onboarding Programs and Employee Retention among Employees of Selected Private Business Organizations in Quezon City

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Abstract

This empirical study explores the relationship between organizational onboarding programs and employee retention among private business organizations in Quezon City. Specifically, it investigates which aspects of onboarding influence employees' intent to stay within the organization. A survey-based approach and quantitative analysis, including the Pearson correlation coefficient, were employed to assess the impact of various onboarding factors on retention. The results indicate that social integration and support provided through the onboarding program exhibit the strongest positive correlation with employee retention, suggesting that employees who feel supported and integrated are more likely to remain with the organization. Conversely, while role clarity and familiarization with organizational culture and values were found to have a weaker but still positive correlation with retention, these factors also contribute to employee commitment. The findings highlight the importance of structured onboarding programs in fostering a sense of belonging and supporting employees' long-term retention within the organization. Based on these insights, organizations are encouraged to design onboarding processes that prioritize social integration, support, and role clarity to improve retention outcomes.

Keywords: *organizational onboarding, employee retention, employee, business organization*

Introduction

“Environments that support their employees in the right way will naturally foster employee engagement,” Aaron Tucker.

The current landscape of employee retention in the BPO sector underscores the growing importance of effective onboarding programs amidst increasing workforce mobility and organizational competition. Trends reveal that companies are investing in structured onboarding processes to address challenges such as high turnover rates, fluctuating employee engagement, and the demand for faster integration into roles.

A well-organized and systematic onboarding program augments employee retention as a result of employee engagement. According to Tim Smith, employee engagement is a human resources concept that describes the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job.

Being financially stable is one of the most aspired statuses of every individual. According to Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), in year 2023, the Philippines have experienced the highest full-year average inflation rate of 6%, since 2008, and as the unpredictability of inflation rate affects the living condition of individuals, one of the best options to handle this, is by developing a career that can support and sustain the needs and comfort of each person, that can also contribute to their growth, personally and professionally.

Being a newcomer to a company, there are various reasons why they choose to stay with the company they work for. Reasons may differ depending on the needs and preferences of each individual. The rate of employee retention of an organization may be affected by their onboarding programs, some new employees may mainly seek inclusion, while old or pre-existing employees seek opportunities and growth; either way, it may be challenging for employees to find a career that gives both comfort and growth.

Employees who switch jobs frequently tend to be known to have less enthusiasm and patience, though these employees might be seeking a job that will give them security and assurance that they cannot receive from their current job, and companies who have structured onboarding programs might have a higher probability of giving these employees what they seek.

There are great chances that the organization is losing reliable, dependable, and talented employees that will bring prosperity and a great future for the company. The company might miss young and vibrant employees who have great potential and bring great contributions for the growth and success of the company due to unsystematic and unorganized onboarding programs; the same goes for pre-existing employees, these employees might lose interest and motivation on thriving for the company because of its lack of structured onboarding programs, and this can result on losing well-experienced employees that can demonstrate their expertise, knowledge, and value to the company.

Investing to develop a structured onboarding program is one of the best ways to help new employees thrive and engage with their new job and environment. This is crucial, since structured onboarding can be an incredible way to set someone up for long-term career success with the company, since employees are considered to provide strength and support continuous growth and success of a company. According to Khadija Aijaz (2023), “Employees are the backbone of a successful company. They are valuable assets that must be invested in, nurtured, and encouraged to be the best they can be.

Research Questions

This study intends to explore the link between onboarding programs of private business organizations in Quezon City and the retention of their employees. This research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. current position?
2. What links between organizational onboarding programs and employee retention among employees of private business organizations in Quezon City?
3. What specific factors of onboarding programs are most effective in retaining employees in private business organizations?
4. How do structured onboarding programs affect and influence the employee's engagement and intent to remain with the organization?

Methodology

Research Design

The primary objective of this research is to determine the effect of onboarding programs on employee retention of private organizations in Quezon city. With this, the researcher employed a descriptive quantitative approach on this research.

Respondents

This study focuses on how onboarding programs affect employee retention. The subjects of this study are entry to senior level employees of BPO (Business Process Outsourcing) companies in Quezon city who have undergone a proper onboarding program by the time they were newly employed. The researcher used an online sample calculator to arrive with 383 respondents.

Instrument

The instruments used in data collection for purposes of getting the required information were the onboarding programs the sample have experienced or the ought to experience, and their level of satisfaction towards the program.

The researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. The gathered data will be carefully read and examined for analysis. Percentage will be used to interpret the profile of the respondents.

Weighted Mean formula is used to analyze responses from the 5-point Likert scale; this will provide a more precise understanding of employee's perceptions regarding onboarding programs.

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient formula to assess the strength and direction of linear relationship between onboarding programs and employee retention.

Procedure

Data refers to all the information a researcher gathers for his study. This section describes data collection procedures. The instruments used in data collection for purposes of getting the required information were the onboarding programs the participants have experienced if there were any, and their thoughts regarding onboarding programs in general.

The researcher will serve a letter of intent duly signed by the researcher, researcher's adviser, and the dean of graduate studies. In securing the data, randomly selected employees of private business organizations will be given a survey questionnaire.

The research survey questionnaires were divided into four parts: 1) The Demographic Profile of the Respondents; 2) General Information; and 3) Retention Factors.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Their Job Level*

	<i>Job Level</i>	
Entry-Level	173	45.17%
Mid-Level	114	29.77%
Senior-Level	96	25.07%
Total	383	100.00%

Table 1 shows the distribution of participants across job levels and shows a diverse representation of employees from various positions within the Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) sector. The largest proportion of participants comes from entry-level positions, accounting for 45.17% of the responses. Mid-level employees make up 29.77% of the participants, highlighting their significant

presence in the study, and finally, senior-level employees represent 25.07% of the participants. The distribution of the respondents indicates a balanced proportion of responses across various job levels, this will allow this research to have a comprehensive analysis of how onboarding programs affect the employees' intent to remain in the organization at different stages of career progression.

Table 2. *Information of the respondents in terms of their length of service in their current organization*

<i>Length Of Service In Current Organization</i>		
Less than 1 year	114	29.77%
1 year - 3 years	74	19.32%
4 years - 6 years	92	24.02%
7 years - 9 years	54	14.10%
10 years and above	49	12.79%
Total	383	100.00%

The table 2 presents the distribution of participants by length of service and shows a significant portion of responses from employees with less than 1 year of service (29.77%), offering insights into the immediate impact of onboarding programs. On the other hand, the smallest group comes from employees with 10 years and above (12.79%), providing perspectives on the long-term effects of onboarding programs. This range allows for a focused analysis of onboarding's impact on both new hires and tenured employees.

Table 3. *Descriptive Statistics for Key Variables*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>SD</i>
Retention Factors	3.47	Agree	0.48
Role Clarity	4.35	Strongly Agree	0.73
Organization's Culture and Values	3.96	Agree	0.83
Social Integration and Support	3.08	Neutral	1.49
Satisfaction with Onboarding Program	2.42	Disagree	1.14
Engagement	3.52	Agree	1.10

Table 3 presents the weighted mean and standard deviation of various variables related to the employees' experience and evaluation of their company's provided onboarding programs.

Retention Factors have a mean of 3.47 and a standard deviation of 0.73, indicating a moderate level of perception about retention, with some variation in responses.

Role Clarity has the highest mean of 4.35 with a standard deviation of 0.73, suggesting that employees feel generally clear about their roles, with consistent responses across participants.

Organization's Culture and Values scores 3.96 with a standard deviation of 0.83, showing that employees have a relatively positive view towards familiarization with their organization's culture, though there is more variability in responses.

Social Integration and Support has a mean of 3.08 and a higher standard deviation of 1.49, indicating that while employees feel moderately supported, there is considerable variation in how supported they feel.

Satisfaction has the lowest mean of 2.42 with a standard deviation of 1.14, suggesting that employees are not very satisfied with the onboarding process, and there is a high level of variation in their satisfaction levels.

Engagement has a mean of 3.52 and a standard deviation of 1.10, showing that overall, employees have a moderate level of engagement, but there is significant variability in how engaged they feel.

The data reveals that Role Clarity stands out as the strongest area, with employees feeling clear about their roles. However, Satisfaction with the Onboarding Program is the lowest, indicating room for improvement in onboarding practices. Social Integration and Support and Engagement show higher variability, suggesting differing experiences among employees.

Table 4. *Correlation of Each Variable*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Correlation With Employee Retention Factors (r)</i>
Role Clarity	0.21
Organization's Culture and Values	0.37
Social Integration and Support	0.65
Satisfaction with Onboarding Program	0.44
Engagement	0.41

Table 4 the Pearson's correlation coefficients between Retention Factors and each of the five independent variables: Role Clarity, Organization's Culture and Values, Social Integration and Support, Satisfaction with Onboarding Program, and Engagement. These coefficients indicate the strength and direction of the relationships between the variables.

Social Integration and Support ($r = 0.65$) has the strongest positive correlation with Retention Factors, suggesting that a supportive

work environment is crucial for retaining employees.

Satisfaction with Onboarding Program ($r = 0.44$) and Engagement ($r = 0.41$) also show moderate positive correlations, indicating that the quality of the onboarding the commitment of employees and enhance retention.

Role Clarity ($r = 0.21$) and Organization's Culture and Values ($r = 0.37$) have weaker but still positive relationships with retention, suggesting that having clear job royals and indication of organization's culture and values alignment is somewhat associated with employee retention, but their impacts are limited.

In conclusion, creating a supportive work environment, providing clear role expectations, and aligning employees with the company culture are essential for enhancing employee retention.

Conclusions

The findings of this study emphasize the significant influence of a supportive work environment in enhancing employee retention. Clear role expectations, strengthened social integration and support, and alignment with the organization's culture and values are essential factors in retaining employees. A supportive work environment shows the strongest correlation with retention, while low satisfaction with the onboarding process indicates a need for immediate improvement in these programs.

While other factors may also have an effect, they happen to have a comparatively smaller influence. Overall, constructing a workplace that promotes strong cooperation and provides clarity in goals and values are keys for keeping top talent and increasing productivity in an organization.

Therefore, to improve employee retention, organizations should focus on enhancing the onboarding experience by creating a more structured process, providing stronger support, and clearly communicating the company's goals and culture to new hires.

This study shows how strong an organization's support system can keep top talents in their organization. Establishing mentorship programs where new employees are paired with more experienced staff will help newcomers build relationships with their seniors, gain proper guidance, and can make them feel more belonged in the organization. Conducting team-building events will also encourage collaboration, trust and a sense of community with the newcomers along with the tenured employees.

Implementing a structured onboarding process that thoroughly explains roles, expectations, and company policies will enable new hires to understand their responsibilities as early as possible. Performance reviews and feedback to keep their employees' personal growth aligned with their organizations.

Establish formal recognition programs and events to celebrate and acknowledge achievements and milestones of personnel, recognizing employees for their hard work builds a sense of belonging and motivation. Provide clear ways for growth within the company, like training programs, leadership development, academic support, to encourage professional and personal growth and keeping them in the organization.

With these programs, organizations can build a supportive environment focused on their employees, since employees should be considered as assets that are appreciated throughout the time. A simple feeling of belonging can be a critical factor for improving employee retention.

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